

**When Desire Outranges the Capability: A Study on the Double-Way Consumption
Phenomena among Young Chinese Luxury Consumers**

Yiran Jia

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financial capability to purchase luxury goods, leading to a phenomenon scholars term “double-way consumption.” With rigorous participant selection, data from 385 valid responses are collected. The suitability of the overall model, along with the constructs’ reliability and validity, is confirmed through CFA. Hypotheses are tested using SEM. The restrictions faced by participants when buying luxury goods. Future research should explore this group’s beliefs within

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s University</auth-address><titles><title>Analysis of the Current Situation and Development of China’s Luxury Goods Market</title><secondary-title>China Market</secondary-title></auth-address>
limited attention has been directed towards the subset of this demographic with lower or no income—a circumstance frequently observed within this group. In China, a phenomenon referred

2. Theoretical background and hypothesis development

2.1. Luxury fashion goods 8

2.1.1. Theoretical background 4

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2.2 Young luxury consumers

Chinese consumers' purchase intentions for luxury clothing: According to the American Generations Report (2013), Generation Z, or Gen Z, encompasses individuals born between the years 1995 and 2009. This generation is characterized by unique traits and characteristics distinct from those of older generations (Thach et al., 2020). Growing up in an

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Double-way consumption, a concept introduced by Chinese sociologist Wang Ning, delineates the consumption strategy adopted by China's middle-income group amidst periods of social

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towards different items or in different contexts (Wang, 2005). Researchers have scrutinized the

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2.4 The theory of planned behavior

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), initially proposed by Ajzen (1985), serves as a behavioral decision-making model aimed at predicting and understanding human actions. It is an extension

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, attitudes and subjective norms are identified as two factors influencing behavioral intention. In the subsequent development of TPB, Ajzen introduced perceived behavioral control as another determinant affecting behavioral intention. TPB has found widespread application across various research domains exploring the relationship between beliefs, attitudes, behavioral intentions, and behaviors (Cunningham and Kwon, 2003). In the context of researching consumer behavior in the luxury goods market, scholars such as Jain et al. (2014) have explored the motivations and behaviors of Indian consumers with regard to luxury purchases. Their study revealed that subjective norm stands out as the primary factor influencing luxury purchase intention, followed closely by attitude. This aligns with findings in other articles, including those by Wantara (2022) and Canguende-Valentim and Vale (2021). Conversely, Muça and Zeqiri (2020) found that perceived behavioral control is the most significant factor influencing purchase intention, followed by subjective norms. Regardless of which factor exerts the greatest influence on luxury purchase intention, researchers have predominantly focused on studying the motivations of broad luxury buyers. There is limited research employing this theory to study specific groups, especially low- to middle-income young demographics seemingly unrelated to luxury purchases. As Ajzen (1991) suggested, the predictive power of the three factors varies across different behaviors and situations. This study aims to use TPB to concentrate on the motivations of specific luxury purchase groups, enriching understanding of luxury purchase groups and the Generation Z era, and further supplementing research on luxury purchase behavior using TPB.

As previously mentioned, TPB posits three conceptually independent determinants of intention. The first determinant is the attitude toward the behavior, which refers to an individual's evaluation or assessment of the behavior under discussion, indicating whether they hold a positive or negative stance (Ajzen, 1991). For this study, attitude refers to the target audience's attitude towards purchasing luxury fashion goods under limited economic conditions, i.e., attitude toward buying luxury fashion goods. In this field of study, scholars have analyzed factors influencing attitudes towards luxury. For example, Gil et al. (2012) analyzed the impact mechanisms of self-dimensions, social consumption motivation, and peer pressure on attitudes towards luxury brands. Additionally, scholars have researched attitudes themselves; Wang et al. (2011) categorized Chinese luxury

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this study, attitude towards buying fashion luxury goods is considered a factor influencing luxury purchase intention, leading to the following hypothesis:

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H1. Attitude towards buying luxury positively affects the luxury fashion goods purchase intention of Gen Z consumers who may apply a double-way consumption strategy.

The second predictor is a social factor known as subjective norm, denoting the perceived social

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pressure experienced when engaging or refraining from a specific behavior (Ajzen, 1991). In the

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H2. Subjective norm positively affects the luxury fashion goods purchase intention of Gen Z consumers who may apply a double-way consumption strategy.

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The third antecedent of intention is the degree of perceived behavioral control, which refers to the perceived ease or difficulty of performing a behavior, reflecting past experiences as well as anticipated obstacles and hindrances (Ajzen, 1991). Unlike TRA, where intention formation solely

depends on motivational factors such as attitudes and subjective norms, Ajzen (1991) argued that subjective norm encapsulates the social pressure perceived by economically constrained young consumers when forming the intention to acquire luxury fashion goods. Prior research, exemplified

by de Araújo and Loureiro (2014), has substantiated the positive impact of subjective norms on the

intention of consumers to purchase luxury goods. Moreover, Jain (2020) identified that subjective

norms can act as a moderator in the relationship between attitude and intentions to purchase luxury

items. In group-oriented investigations, Aliyev and Wagner (2018) conducted a comparative

analysis of the influence of subjective norms on luxury value perceptions, drawing distinctions

between collectivist and individualist perspectives. In this study, subjective norm is believed to

impact on perceived behavioral control. Additionally, various studies have validated the positive influence of perceived behavioral control on luxury purchase intention, such as Zhang et al. (2020) and Jain (2020). Building on the findings of previous research, this study assumes that perceived behavioral control has a positive impact on the purchase intention of Gen Z consumers who exhibit double-way consumption behavior when purchasing luxury fashion goods, leading to the following hypothesis:

H3. Perceived behavioral control positively affects the luxury fashion goods purchase intention of Gen Z consumers who may apply a double-way consumption strategy.

3. Methods

3.1 Measurement instrument

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bipolar adjective scales based on TPB. These scales cover attitude toward the behavior, subjective

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and perceived behavioral control, each comprising two questions, while behavioral intention

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3.2 Data collection

This study collected data through online surveys. During the questionnaire distribution process, it was crucial to restrict the information of respondents. Three methods were used to ensure this: firstly, the requirement for respondents to fill out the questionnaire was repeatedly emphasized

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3.3 Characteristics of the sample

To better understand the Gen Z group that adopts the double-way consumption strategy when

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Furthermore, several scales employed in the realm of luxury purchase motivation research, including those developed by Gao et al. (2009), Li et al. (2012), and Zhang and Kim (2013), were

for 54.5%, slightly higher than males. Approximately 75% of respondents had received a bachelor's degree or above, while around 20% had received a college education, and only about 4% had not received any form of higher education. Regarding occupational status, only 2.6% of respondents were unemployed, while 35% were students, and the remaining respondents were employed. In terms of hometown cities, 13.5% of respondents came from super first-tier cities (Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou, or Shenzhen), while approximately 54% came from first- or second-tier cities, around 28% came from third- or fourth-tier cities, and a small number came from fifth-tier and below cities. Concerning family annual income, around 30% of respondents had an annual income ranging from 100,000 to 200,000 (RMB), and a similar proportion had an income ranging from 300,000 to 400,000. Additionally, approximately 12.7% and 14% of respondents had a family annual income of less than 100,000 or between 300,000 and 500,000, respectively.

Variable	N
Gender	
Male	
Female	
Education	
High school or below	
College	
Undergraduate	
Postgraduate or above	
Occupation	
Unemployed	
Student	
Employed	
City	
Super tier 1 cities	
Tier 1 or 2 cities	
Tier 3 or 4 cities	
Tier 5 cities or below	
Family average annual income (RMB)	
Below 100,000	
Above 500,000	

4. Data analysis and results 8

's fit to the data (Hair et al., 2010). The overall goodness of fit of the CFA measurement model was satisfactory, as indicated by various fit indices. The Chi-square test resulted in a value of $\chi^2=161$, with $p < 0.05$, $df=48$, and $\chi^2/ df= 3.35$, indicating a reasonable model fit. Additionally, the

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Descriptive statistic, correlation matrix and AVE

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Cronbach' alpha and composite reliability

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability
	0.81	0.81
Subjective norm	0.75	0.76
Perceived behavioral control	0.81	0.82
	0.78	0.79

Factor loading results

Construct	Scale item	Factor loading
	Under the current economic conditions, my view towards purchasing fashion luxury goods is favorable.	

Subjective norm

Perceived behavioral control

' attitudes towards and intentions to purchase luxury fashion goods, with a positive effect ($\beta=0.19$, purchase intentions of these consumers ($\beta=0.15$, $SE=0.07$, T statistic= 2.07). H3 examines the group ($\beta=0.50$, $SE=0.08$, T statistic= 6.17), confirming the significance of this factor in shaping

Hypotheses testing results

Hypothesis	Estimate(β)	SE	T statistic	Result
Attitude $\rightarrow$ Intention			**	Supported
Subjective norm $\rightarrow$ Intention			*	Supported
Perceived behavioral control $\rightarrow$			***	Supported

* Significant at $p<0.05$; ** Significant at $p<0.01$; *** Significant at $p<0.001$

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